

MEASUREMENTS OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY AND THERMAL
CONTACT RESISTANCE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS
FOR SPACE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

An apparatus has been designed and implemented for measuring thermal conductivity and thermal contact resistance as a function of the applied pressure and average temperature at the interface, in vacuo.

Results are reported concerning metals: stainless steel aluminium, copper and composite materials such as glass and carbon fiber/epoxy for space applications.

The pressure ranged from 0 to $28 \cdot 10^6$ Pa and the temperature from 30 to 90°C. The expected behaviour of thermal resistance, decreasing with increasing pressure, is recognizable.

Resulting uncertainties turn out to be rather high (10 ÷ 40%) but still compatible with normal design requirements.

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge of the thermal properties of composite materials is fundamental for a proper thermal design of spacecrafts.

Actually the composite materials are growing in interest, mainly in space applications, because they combine good thermo-mechanical properties with low density. For these materials, however, extensive and systematic thermal data are scarcely available, especially in comparison with the rate

of innovation in this field.

This is particularly true for contact resistance (composite/metal or composite/composite) which, on the other hand, may have not a negligible importance in building up the overall thermal resistance because in space structures heat flux is transmitted through different contacting materials (composite/composite/metal) in a vacuum environment.

The aim of this work is to collect data in this matter and to investigate mainly the influence of the pressure, and temperature as well, on carbon-glass composite materials.

BACKGROUND

Thermal contact resistance depends on several macroscopic parameters: for instance pressure, surface roughness, hardness, interstitial material.

The heat flux is transmitted across the actual contact spots ("joint spots") via conduction and through the gaps via convection/conduction in the trapped air (if any) and via radiation.

From a microscopic point of view the heat flux is transmitted in the contacting spots mainly via phonons (vibrational quanta) scattered at the interface due to the different sound speed in the two contacting media. Some models [1] have phonon scattering effect inside both materials in the vicinity of the contact boundary.

Several models have been proposed to compute thermal contact resistance. In the following, are briefly reviewed two models by Antonetti et alii [9] and Thomas et alii [11]. The first is concerned to an analytical approach, while the latter to a semiempirical one.

According to the first approach the following main assumptions are adopted:

- a) the contacting surfaces are free of oxide films;
- b) the gaps between interfacial surfaces are free of any conducting fluid or material, so that the contact occurs in a vacuum;
- c) radiative heat transfer is negligible;

- d) the contacting surfaces are nominally flat from a macroscopic point of view, but microscopically rough and asperities heats obly to a Gaussian distribution;
- e) the real contact area consists of circular, isothermal, microcontact spots uniformly distributed over the apparent area.

Then the Fourier equation is solved in the vicinity of the interface and heat flux is calculated across the joints realized by the contact of opposite asperities or contacting spots.

The resulting expression for contact resistance R is [9]:

$$R = 0.46 \left(\frac{\sigma}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1} + \frac{1}{\lambda_2} \right) \left(\frac{P}{H} \right)^{-0.93} \quad (1)$$

where: P = apparent contact pressure, H = microhardness, σ = RMS surface roughness, m = average asperities slope, λ_i = thermal conductivity of medium i.

According to the second approach [11], the dimensional analysis leads to two dimensionless groups:

$$C^* = \frac{C}{\sigma \lambda} \quad \text{and} \quad W^* = \frac{W}{\sigma^2 H} \quad (2)$$

where W is the applied load and C = contact area/R the conductance.

The proposed relationship between the conductance and the load is [11]:

$$C^* = \gamma (W^*)^\beta \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma = 3.7$ and $\beta = 0.66$ when at least a surface is Aluminium, while $\gamma = 0.26$ and $\beta = 0.96$ for stainless steel junctions only.

MEASUREMENT CRITERIA

The apparatus was intended to approximate the following idealized situation (Fig. 1).

An uniform pressure is applied to the $n \geq 1$ samples by means of two stainless steel cylinders.

Nevertheless the system: upper cylinder + samples + lower cylinder, should simulate a perfect heat pipe with a linear temperature distribution along the z axis and an uniform temperature distribution through any cross-section of the cylinder at constant z (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Specimen temperature distribution.

In these ideal conditions, knowing the temperature gradient dT/dz and the thermal conductivity of stainless steel, the constant (along z axis) heat flux \dot{Q} through any normal section of the cylinder is known.

Therefore the following equation holds:

$$\dot{Q} = H_S \Delta T_S \quad (4)$$

where H_S is the overall thermal transmission through the sample and ΔT is the temperature difference between surfaces 1 and 2.

This temperature drop is obtained, from experimental point of view, by extrapolating temperature distribution along the z axis in the cylinders.

H_S can be put in the form:

$$H_S = \frac{1}{2R_{F/S} + n(s/\lambda) + (n-1)R_{S/S}} \quad (5)$$

where: $R_{F/S}$ = thermal resistance at the interface: stainless steel/sample;
 $R_{S/S}$ = thermal resistance at the interface: sample/sample; s = thickness of

the samples; λ = thermal conductivity of samples.

By applying (1) and (2) to the following case:

- a) $n \geq 1$
- b) $n = 1$

and extrapolating (1), (2) for $n = 0$ (case c), three equations are obtained in the three unknowns $R_{F/S}$, λ , $R_{S/S}$.

If λ is known only a), b) steps are required. Of course the final accuracy on $R_{F/S}$, λ , $R_{S/S}$ largely depends on the accuracy of ΔT 's measurements and, in particular, the accuracy on $R_{F/S}$, $R_{S/S}$ depends on the actual values of s/λ in the sense that $2R_{F/S}$, ns/λ , $(n-1)R_{S/S}$ should not differ so much from each other.

For high pressure and compressible samples, in order to calculate λ , variation of s as a function of pressure has to be taken into account.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

In Fig. 2 the schematic view of the experimental chamber and of the actual apparatus [12] is illustrated below.

Six main sections are derived and recognizable:

- 1) a section provided to apply a variable pressure to the samples;
- 2) a section devoted to provide a vacuum environment allowing the deformation induced by the varying pressure applied from outside;
- 3) a section to control the background temperature of the sample;
- 4) a section devised to build up a controlled gradient along the stainless steel cylinders which simulates the heat pipe;
- 5) a section devised to size the thermal field, in particular the temperature distribution along the axis of the cylinders.

Section 1 is realized essentially by means of a screw system which allows changing by hand the basic strain applied to the cylinders.

These latters transmit the load to the samples.

Figure 2. Schematic view and experimental apparatus.

The applied load is monitored by means of a standard strain gauge cell whose output is displayed by a digital voltmeter.

The pressure initially changes as a consequence of the thermal expansion of the entire apparatus, when a thermal gradient is applied to the cylinders.

The final pressure recorded, was the steady state value of the pressure reached after the thermal steady state condition was achieved.

Section 2 consists of a stainless steel vacuum chamber and a stainless steel bellows which allows deformation in the vertical direction.

Section 3 consists of:

- a) an internal copper coiled piping for warm/hot water or liquid nitrogen;
- b) an external copper coil similar to a);
- c) an internal electric resistance;
- d) extensive external, easily removable, thermal insulation-consisting of a removable external tank which contains the vacuum chamber; the tank is

completely filled by polystyrene pellets for an overall thickness of ≥ 5 cm.

The piping coarsly controls the environment temperature (or reference temperature or mean temperature of the cylinder). For low temperature runs liquid nitrogen replaced hot/warm water in the piping system.

Fine tuning of the background temperature is achieved (both for ambient and low temperatures cases) by means of an electric resistance (item c).

Section 4 consists of an electric resistance around the top of the upper cylinder.

Section 5 consists of a set of 6 thermocoaxes inserted in the cylinder up to the cylinder axis.

CHARACTERISTICS OF SPECIMENS

The geometrical data of specimens are listed in Tab. 1.

The alloy specimens were cut from a commercial sheet with a standard surface roughness and composition.

TABLE 1. Specimens sizes.

Materials	Thickness (cm)	Diameter (cm)
Al: Anticorodal 11T6	0.10	2.10
Cu: UNI 2528	0.10	2.10
Stainless Steel AISI 4340	0.10	2.10
Glass Fiber Laminate	0.17	2.10
Graphite-Epoxy Laminate	0.20	2.10

The glass fiber specimens were cut from a standard printed circuit boards, and the resin binder was a bisphenol A epoxy matrix. The fibers were E-type glass filaments. The 16-layer carbon fiber laminate was quasi-isotropic with the following stacking sequence $[0/45/-45/90]_{2S}$ manufactured by the University of Dayton (USA) for USA-Air Force.

The prepreg is composed by a Carbon Fiber Type IM6 and the matrix is an amine-cured epoxy resin type Magnamite AS4/3501-6, both manufactured by Hercules.

RESULTS AND COMMENTS

The results are reported in Figs. 3 ÷ 6 where thermal contact conductance h_C ($W m^{-2} K^{-1}$) = R^{-1} is plotted versus pressure (Pa).

The results concerning thermal contact resistance metal versus metal (Figs. 3 ÷ 5) show to be in reasonable agreement with data published by ().

So that equivalent confidence is transferred to results concerning contact resistance composite versus composite or composite versus metal.

Thermal conductivity, for composite materials, is shown, as expected, to be essentially independent on the applied pressure (Fig. 7) in the range of experienced pressures.

The temperature shows not to play a relevant role, in the narrow range experienced.

Thermal contact conductance, on the other hand, is found, still as expected, to increase increasing the applied load.

The average gradient turns out to be some $10^{-3} (W m^{-2} K^{-1}/Pa)$.

The uncertainties affecting the results and shown in Figs. 3 ÷ 6, are estimated assuming an overall uncertainty on the leading temperature differences of ± 0.1 K even in the extrapolation procedures.

The observed average values of the thermal contact resistance and of conductivity for composite materials suggest that the relevance of the contact resistance on the overall thermal resistance is important mainly in the case of a small thickness of the composites themselves and mainly for the case of metal/composite resistance.

As a matter of fact resistance is comparable to $\approx 1/3$ of the resistance of a specimen 1 mm thick.

In Fig. 8 the curves calculated with (1) by adjusting the constant are also reported.

A reasonable agreement, at least as a general behaviour is pointed out.

In Fig. 9 the comparison between experimental data and the correlation suggested by (3) is shown.

In particular the following relation derived from (3) is used:

$$h_C = \gamma' P^\beta.$$

Figure 3. Experimental Values of Thermal Contact Conductance between Stainless Steel/Aluminium (a) and Aluminium/Aluminium (b) Interface.

Figure 4. Experimental Values of Thermal Contact Conductance between Stainless Steel/Copper (a) and Copper/Copper (b) Interface.

Figure 5. Experimental Values of Thermal Contact Conductance between Stainless Steel/Graphite-Epoxy Laminate (a) and Stainless Steel/Glass-Epoxy Laminate (b) Interface.

Figure 6. Experimental Values of Thermal Contact Conductance between Graphite-Epoxy Laminate/Graphite-Epoxy Laminate (a) and Glass-Epoxy Laminate/Glass-Epoxy Laminate (b) Interface.

Figure 7. Experimental Values of Thermal Transversal Conductivity of Graphite-Epoxy (a) and Glass-Epoxy (b) Laminates Versus Pressure.

Figure 8. Comparison between Experimental and Theoretical Values for Stainless Steel/Aluminium (Curve 1) and Stainless Steel/Copper (Curve 2) Interfaces.

Figure 9. Contact Conductance: Comparison between Experimental and Theoretical Values for Stainless Steel/Aluminium Interface.

The multiplying constant γ' is adjusted using the data while the constant β is unchanged.

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